

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Nursing research goals in pediatric care

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Abstract

The creation of knowledge by pediatric nurse scientists that informs and directs everyday nursing practice is essential to delivering safe and effective nursing care to children. The health of our children is at stake due to current statistics showing a steady decline in pediatric nurses and a lack of pediatric nurse scientists with PhDs. The objectives of this paper are to: Summarize the demands on pediatric health care. Express our concern that there are insufficient pediatric nurse scientists to produce the fundamental knowledge needed to direct pediatric nursing practice. Discuss the factors that may affect the number of pediatric nurse scientists. Make recommendations for nursing leaders, faculty, and professional nursing organizations to increase the depth of knowledge in pediatric health care.

Keywords: Care; Goals; Nursing; Pediatric; Research

1. Introduction

Excellence in Pediatric nursing is shown by how well research is used to give safe and effective nursing care to children and their families based on evidence from practice. We argue that the lack of PhD-educated Pediatric research scientists hurts the nursing profession's ability to improve and meet the growing needs of children's health care. It is impossible to overestimate the significance of Pediatric research. Early experiences, especially during pregnancy, set the stage for a baby's long-term health and happiness. The biological embedding of stress-induced physiologic responses causes neurodevelopmental problems and learning disorders, high-risk behaviours, and subsequent chronic physical and mental illness in infants and children exposed to prenatal insults, toxic stress, poverty, maltreatment, or other social, economic, and experiential adversities. The physiologic loads accumulated over time are the early causes of diseases that develop later in life. Nursing research focusing on health burdens during pregnancy, infancy, and childhood is necessary to create, evaluate, and implement interventions to improve the lives of children and families. In the end, nurse-led Pediatric research is required to improve health outcomes throughout a person's life. Although research aimed at enhancing children's health is conducted in various fields, this piece focuses on nurses who work in Pediatric research. In this commentary, we: Outline the current demands on Pediatric health care. Express our concern that there are insufficient Pediatric nurse scientists to produce the fundamental knowledge needed to direct Pediatric nursing practice. Discuss the factors that may affect the number of Pediatric nurse scientists. Suggest specific actions for nursing leaders, faculty, and professional nursing organizations to increase the depth and breadth of Pediatric nursing knowledge. For the sake of this study, we refer to Pediatric nurse scientists as registered nurses with a PhD who work in academic, clinical, or community settings. We have ongoing research projects about children's health and well-being. While PhD-trained nurses are specifically educated to develop knowledge through nurse-led research teams, nursing science has grown to include doctoral-level education preparing experts for clinical practice. The term "Pediatrics" is

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used in this essay by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) definition of children, which encompasses neonates, babies, kids, and adolescents [1].

2. Overview

This review looked at eight articles from the last ten years that reported on pediatric nursing research objectives from the nurses' point of view. The goal was to develop global themes and subthemes to guide future research. All articles employed consensus-building techniques to write priorities that the freshly created CREDIT recommendations deemed calibre highly. The results show that nurses must provide evidence-based care in all settings and collaborate with researchers and other team members to produce research evidence. All the articles that were looked at for this analysis focused on patient safety research priorities, such as prescription mistakes, serious events, and hospital-acquired infections [2].

Over the past ten years, adverse events in pediatric inpatient settings have drawn more attention and continue to be a significant problem. According to a recent study from the USA, there was no improvement in the number of adverse events between 2007 and 2012. The authors of a Cochrane analysis from 2015 concluded that there was insufficient data to support best practices for guarding against pediatric hospital medical errors. Safety also included preventing child mistreatment, abuse, and neglect. A study of USA nurse practitioners revealed that 51% of respondents did not ask parents questions concerning domestic abuse, even though nurses play a crucial role in hospitals, child- and school health, and the disclosure of child maltreatment. Children themselves have been said to place high importance on patient safety. Therefore, research to improve child safety should continue to be a top priority in all healthcare settings. Because of the diagnosis, pediatric nurses treat children at all developmental stages and locations. For instance, nurses are essential to providing children and their families with the best end-of-life care possible. According to a recent integrated review of parental perspectives on end-of-life care, future studies should concentrate on factors that promote the growth of trust and effective communication between family members and medical professionals. Thus, this review's research topics for long-term sickness and end-of-life care are still relevant. Children and their families frequently struggle with moving between contexts and situations. A child may transition from being healthy to ill, and one when moving from pediatric care to adult care or living in the community if they have a chronic disease. The priorities for care transition outlined in this analysis are still relevant because a Cochrane evaluation on the change from pediatric to adult care found that there were insufficient suitable papers to conduct a review [3].

There is literature on family-centred care (FCC), and FCC research priorities were substantially represented in this evaluation. This may reflect the continued difficulties with operationalizing family-centred care (FCC), in many settings. In this analysis, the FCC and child-centred care claims were put together to form the child-centred care (CCC) theme, which uses more modern language and ways of thinking. More research is required to inform the implementation, measurement, and evaluation of FCC interventions. Psychological health deals with problems with the mind, such as bad mental health after a stay in the hospital or worry and pain caused by being away from family while in the hospital. According to reports, these are some main reasons children and young people are burdened. The healthcare trajectory of a kid can result in long-term stress and issues like impaired cognition, poor sleep, fear, pain, worry, and depression, regardless of the illness' severity, diagnosis, or handicap [4].

More research is needed to prevent kids and teens from getting stressed out and having mental health problems. Improving nursing care for children and their families was one of the chosen nursing research areas, along with enhancing the profession, the workplace, and working circumstances. Interestingly, the papers only mentioned improving or measuring the quality of nursing care and putting evidence into practice. Even though putting clinical practice guidelines into action is a great way to promote uniformity and proof, it is still hard to guarantee that they will be used consistently and widely. Integrating evidence into clinical nursing practice is frequently tricky since it calls for altering behaviour and maintaining that change over time. This review suggests that implementation research, which is the scientific study of ways to get research results used in everyday practice, should get more attention in nursing research than it has [5].

Today's academic programs and clinical facilities prioritize the themes and sub-themes that make up the findings. The overarching themes of evidence-based practice, patient safety, family-centred care, and end-of-life care are already evident in nursing literature, presumably reflecting the influence of priorities established over the previous ten years on nursing research. The research priorities listed are still crucial for improving children's quality of nursing care. The 234 had research priorities covering a wide range of topics. However, some are less well-represented than others. For example, suppose research priorities were set today. In that case, they might include communication issues like the use of translators in pediatric nursing since more and more refugee children and their families need medical care. The most critical problem with the review was that only nurses' opinions were used to decide the research goals. It is unclear if

their goals are the same as those of other groups, especially children and their families, who are the prominent people who need nursing care. This review looked at the research goals of pediatric nurses. It did this by putting together themes and sub-themes from eight articles from three continents and ten years of research. All of the studies used consensus-building methods to report their priorities, and since the papers from different sources were used, critical or acute care got a lot of attention. The theme of research to advance patient safety was mentioned in every article. Although they don't cover all practice areas for pediatric nurses, the highlighted priorities still apply to current practice. There were no reports of community nursing research priorities for children's and adolescents' health. Also, and this may be the most important thing, only the nurses' opinions were used to report on the priorities. It is unknown what the other parties' viewpoints are, particularly those of the families and the children [6].

3. Conclusion

This post marks the start of a crucial nursing conversation on what is perceived as a severe shortage of pediatric nurse scientists. We described the issue as we saw it, highlighting various aspects of addressing it and offering general and specific Thought-provoking suggestions for encouraging the first steps towards influencing change. Pediatric nursing and pediatric nursing science should have a bright future. Care for everyone. Without nurses with particular knowledge of the requirements of ill children and the strategies for promoting children's growth and maintaining good health, at least one-third of the world is at risk of receiving poor medical treatment. There are several obstacles to preserving the existing quantity of pediatric nurses. These difficulties put even fewer nursing scientists at risk. They engaged in significant research on child care and the giving of medical care. We enjoin nursing leaders, faculty members, and professional organizations to Think about and take actions that will support pediatric Nursing and scientific training for aspiring pediatric nurses strengthening and improving nursing care of babies, kids, and families.No specific grant was provided for this project supporting organizations from the public, private, or nonprofit sectors.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest declared by the authors

Statement of ethical approval

This evaluation does not require ethical approval because no patient data will be collected. Plagiarism, confidentiality, malfeasance, data falsification and/or falsification, double publishing and/or submission, and duplication are among the ethical problems examined in this study.

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